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Erasmus+ Programme

(ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-1)

**Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the
West Balkans**

(Project 101129182 — Homo Digitalis)

<PROJECT MANAGEMENT PLAN>

<D1.2 >

**LOGOS University College
Work Package 1**

**Version: 1
6 December 2023**

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This Project Management Plan outline the scope, goals, budget, timeline, deliverables and milestones of the Homo Digitalis project and sets out the processes, procedures, roles and obligations, in which the HOMO DOGITALIS project partner HEIs shall collaborate. The processes and procedures described herein aim at ensuring that an effective and transparent method is in place for the efficient delivery of the Project. This document complements existing project documentation including the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement, which should be used in conjunction with them.

This document was approved by the project’s General Management Committee and project Management Committee in the course of its kick-off meeting in Tirana, Albania. This project management plan, including the management strategy, with its communication and reporting components, was drafted and developed by LOGOS University College as lead beneficiary of the project and ahead of this meeting, debated, amended and edited pursuant to timely consultations with partner institutions.

Partners:

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DOCUMENT CONTROL

Project acronym:	HOMO DIGITALIS
Project Title:	Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the
Project No.	101129182
Date:	6 December 2023
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Reviewer:	
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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

SEN	Sensitive / Restricted to a group specified by the HOMO DOGITALIS
PUB	Public

TYPE

R	Document, report
DEC	Website / patent filings, videos, etc.

PRODUCT

D	Deliverable
M	Milestone

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Abbreviations

AAB	Kolegji AAB (EDU invest shpk), Prishtina, Kosovo*
CA	Consortium Agreement
DH&EM	Digital Humanities and Educational Media
EC	European Commission
EACEA	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
ENQA	European Association for Quality Assurance
ESG	Standards & Guidelines for QA in the European Higher Education Area
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GEI	Leibniz-Institut Fur Bildungsmedien Georg-Eckert-Institut
GMC	General Management Committee
HD	Homo Digitalis
HEI	Higher Education Institution
IBC-M	International Business College – Mitrovica, Kosovo*
LOGOS	LOGOS University College, Tirana, Albania
OVGU	Otto-Von-Guericke-Universitaet Magdeburg, Germany
PMC	Project Management Committee
PMP	Project Management Plan
PQMC	Project Quality Monitoring Committee
QA	Quality Assurance
QMAP	Quality Monitoring Action Plan
SEEU	South-East European University Tetovo, North Macedonia
SSST	Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola za Nauku i Tehnologiju PU / Sarajevo School of Science & Technology, Bosnia and Herzegovina
U_POLIS	Universiteti Polis shpk (Polis shpk) / Polis University, Tirana, Albania
UNSA	Univerzitet u Sarajevu, Bosnia and Herzegovina
UPatra	Panepistimio Patron / University of Patra, Greece
WB	West Balkans
WP	Work Package
WPLs	Work Package Leaders

1. Introduction

This document is compiled under the aegis of LOGOS in the context of the HOMO DIGITALIS Project. Its development falls under WP-1 (Management), led by LOGOS University College (LOGOS). This Project Management Plan (PMP) is based on the project's specifications set forth in the Grant Agreement, and in accordance with Standards and Guidelines for Quality Assurance in the European Higher Education Area (ESG) document developed by the European Network for Quality Assurance (ENQA) in Higher Education (2015), as well as literature review (see appendix Bibliography, 10.5).

The HOMO DIGITALIS (HD) project management plan comprises an all-inclusive work plan, whereby the project's work packages are analysed in groups of tasks leading to deliverables. For the implementation of tasks appropriate resources have been allocated corresponding to the members of the project team.

The main aim of the HD Project is to contribute to bridging the digital humanities and educational media divide in the West Balkans (WB).

1.1. Project Management Plan (PMP): scope and principles

The scope of the HD Project Management Plan is to give a detailed overview of the most relevant managerial aspects of the project, setting out the rules and responsibilities of the partners, aimed at ensuring a good quality and progress of the work.

Eight principles have been followed in compiling this PMP:

1. Clarity of Project Management Structures.
2. Adhering to the project's aim and objectives.
3. Clear and well-defined roles, expectations and responsibilities.
4. Sharp change management provisions.
5. Well-weighed risk management provisions.
6. Widest possible enhancement of value-adding capacity.
7. Clear set-up of performance management baselines.
8. Efficiency of communication plan.

1.2 Project Management Plan: objectives

This PMP is to set up a series of solid management provisions, to guarantee timelines, efficient governance structures, collaboration arrangements and well-defined and realistic allocation of responsibilities.

The objectives of PMP are:

- to guarantee project's resilience and smooth functioning
- to coordinate project activities by the involved parties and monitor progress against time plan and budget (resources consumed)

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- to supervise compliance with the program obligations
- to handle risks both pro-actively and reactively
- to update the Partnership Agreement based on project start decisions and finalization of outcomes after completion of each key output
- to report everything on a regular basis in order to ensure all stakeholders are on the same line
- to subcontract external auditor for the project quality evaluation
- to encourage and support the use of green practices and digital transformation of network.

1.3 Relation to other project documents

In the event of discrepancy between documents, this PMP is overruled by the Grant Agreement including its Annexes and the Consortium Agreement.

1.4 Project reference, duration, budget and EC Contribution

Project number:	101129182
Project name:	Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the West Balkans
Project acronym:	HOMO DIGITALIS
Call:	ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE
Topic:	ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-1
Type of action:	ERASMUS Lump Sum
Maximum grant by EC:	397 670.00 euro
Grants Granting authority:	European Education and Culture Executive Agency
Project starting date:	1 November 2023
Project end date:	31 October 2025
Project duration:	24 months

Key words: Innovation in Learning, Teaching and Assessment Practices supported by Digital Technologies; Curriculum Design and Development; Sustainable Development Goals; Quality Education; Humanities; Digital Humanities, Digital Media in Education.

1.5 Contractual Documents

- Grant Agreement (GA)
- Consortium Agreement (CA)

1.6 Partners

Lead beneficiary:

1. LOGOS University College (LOGOS), PIC 887981748, Tirana, Albania.

Other beneficiaries:

2. Universiteti POLIS Shpk (POLIS Shpk), PIC 954870232, Tirana, Albania.
3. International Business College Mitrovica (IBC-M), PIC 915740529, Mitrovica, Kosovo*.
4. Kolegji AAB (EDU Invest Shpk), PIC 948683863, Pristina 10000, Kosovo*.
5. Univerzitet U Sarajevu (UNSA), PIC 995549995, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.
6. Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola za Nauku i Tehnologiju PU (SSST), PIC 991577942, Sarajevo, Bosnia and Herzegovina.
7. South East European University Tetovo (SEEU), PIC 998142417, Tetovo, Republic of North Macedonia,
8. Otto-Von-Guericke-Universitaet Magdeburg (OVGU), PIC 999873285, Magdeburg, Germany.
9. Panepistimio Patron (UPatra), PIC 999894528, Patras, Greece.

Associated Partner (another participant involved in the action):

The following entity which cooperate with the beneficiaries will participate in the action as ‘associated partner’:

10. Leibniz-Institut Fur Bildungsmedien Georg-Eckert-Institut (Leibniz Institute for Educational Media, GEI), PIC 984042400, Germany.

Associated partner must implement the action tasks attributed to them in Annex 1 in accordance with Article 11. In this case, the associated partner do not charge contributions to the action (no lump sum contributions) and the costs for their tasks.

2. Project structure

2.1 Work packages list/overview

The project’s outputs are principally its deliverables, whose completion’s progress is monitored through milestones. These are set out in the GA, Annex 1, Part A. These products will be delivered, mostly, in the form of reports. Broadly, the project is divided in 6 WPs, listed below.

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- 1. Work package 1: Project Management & Coordination**
Lead Beneficiary: LOGOS University College (LOGOS)
- 2. Work package 2: Curriculum Development**
Lead Beneficiary: Polis University (U_Polis)
- 3. Work package 3: Development of academic staff & student learning competencies**
Lead Beneficiary: University of Patra (UPatra)
- 4. Work package 4: Development of Digital Humanities and Educational Media Laboratories**
Lead Beneficiary: South-East European University (SEEU)
- 5. Work package 5: Quality Assurance**
Lead Beneficiary: International Business College – Mitrovica (IBC-M)
- 6. Work package 6: Dissemination & exploitation**
Lead Beneficiary: Sarajevo School of Science & Technology (SSST)

2.1 Deliverables

Table 1 List of deliverables

No	WP	D	Deliverable name	Description	LEAD	Type	Dissem.	Due Date
1	WP1	D1.1	Start of project implementation and setting up the PM Structures.	The deliverable comprises of the kick-off meeting, as well as the operationalization of the project management decision-making structures: GMC and PMC.	LOGOS	R	SEN	31-Dec-23
2	WP1	D1.2	Project Management Plan (PMP)	The PMP will describe the Internal procedures (project organization, communication plan, risk management, escalation procedures, templates, etc.) to be followed in the context of the project in order to ensure the fulfilment of the objectives, specify standards for the creation and management of project products and establish project monitoring, reporting, evaluation and correction procedures.	LOGOS	R	Public	31-Dec-23
3	WP1	D1.3	Revision of Needs and Wants Assessment Document.	The needs and wants assessment conducted upon this project application will be deepened and enhanced, for identifying issues & training topics that previously slipped unnoticed (special focus on participants with fewer opportunities). The document shall contain a section on the concrete courses to be created or revised in response to the identified needs and wants.	LOGOS	R	SEN	31-Dec-23
4	WP1	D1.4	Mid-Term Report	Mid-term report includes a managerial and a financial report component outlining progress achieved up until the middle of the project's lifetime.	LOGOS	R	SEN	31-Oct-24

12	WP3	D3.3	Study visit & training at the University of Patra	2 days Study visit at UPatra (12 particip. from WBs, 1 staff and 1 student from each University) This study visit will be realized at UPatra. Academic staff & students are expected to attend from all partner HEIs from the WB. The visit will be in the workshop format; staff and students will be presented with real examples of cooperation, how can they develop multilateral and multi-disciplinary project. Students and staff through examples will be motivated on how to work with their colleagues from the Consortium, but also with other stakeholders such as industry etc. At least 3 project concepts will be prepared as a final output.	UPatra	R	SEN	28-Feb-25
13	WP4	D4.1	Set up and equip Digital Humanities and Educational Media Laboratories	All partners HEIs, will establish laboratories, in line with the objectives of the project, for the purpose of supporting teaching, learning and scientific research in the disciplines. Also, Digital Labs will be set up for the purpose of supporting small-scale national and international projects aimed at promoting cultural and green heritage. The tendering procedure at each partner country Institution will start from the month 3, of the first year of the project implementation.	SEEU	R	SEN	31-Aug-24
14	WP4	D4.2	Promotion of innovation in humanities reinforced by ICT methods and tools in collaboration with labour market	This deliverable consists in a report on the ways in which partner HEIs in collaboration with labour market partners (evidenced by MOU) have promoted ICT-led innovation in Humanities.	SEEU	R	SEN	30-Sep-25
15	WP4	D4.3	Establishment of international cooperation in DH&EM	This deliverable addresses the sustainability challenge of the project. It is anticipated that, in the course of the project's lifetime, partner HEIs will establish international cooperation in the DH&EM disciplines, evidenced by MOUs and collaboration projects at an international level.	SEEU	R	SEN	30-Sep-25
16	WP5	D5.1	Development of the Quality Monitoring Action Plan (QMAP)	The QMAP will contain information regarding the Project organization; Processes for the implementation, administration and quality assurance of the project; methodology for reporting to the Commission and escalation paths in the event of problems.	IBC-M	R	SEN	31-Dec-23
17	WP5	D5.2	Specification of quality assurance indicators for digital and humanities competencies	Setting quality assurance indicators for digital and humanities competencies to be monitored by the QMC.	IBC-M	R	SEN	29-Feb-24

22	WP6	D6.2	Dissemination products and tools	This deliverable consists in the conceptualization and layout design of the project's dissemination products and tools, to be later used throughout the life-cycle of the projects to advance its clause to wider audiences beyond the consortium: Project website; Social Media; Backlinks from partner's websites; Dissemination Wiki; On-line promotional material (6 newsletters, 12 press releases, 4 articles, 4 publications, infographics; Project flyers (900 Items / 3 pages, suggested dimensions: 13.97 x 21.59; suggested paper type: gloss, 130 gsm); Project info kit (the brochure, the project presentations of objectives & expected results, the logo & banner designs, newsletters, press releases, publications and an offline version of the project site & project material (120 Items / Project branded USB). Suggested dimensions: 23X32 closed, 46X32 open paper: 300gr; suggested paper type: Illustration-Velvet; suggested printing: colour offset. Four roll up banners: designed to be used during physical events (Dimensions: 2x1 perpendicular).	UNSA	DEC	PU	31-Mar-24
23	WP6	D6.3	First Multiplier Event in Sarajevo	Communications and the first multiplier event is to be held in Sarajevo with the participation of faculty & students from partner WB HEIs. The event will be transmitted also online, while policy makers, other HEIs & social partners will be invited to facilitate high-level discussions and policy priorities.	UNSA	OTHER	PU	31-Oct-24
24	WP6	D6.4	Second Multiplier Event in Prishtina	Communications & the second multiplier event is to be held in Prishtina with the participation of faculty & students from partner WB HEIs. The event will be transmitted also online; policy makers, other HEIs & social partners will be invited to facilitate high-level discussions and policy priorities.	UNSA	OTHER	PU	30-Jun-25
25	WP8	D6.5	Second Multiplier Event in Tirana	This deliverable is a report on a conference presenting the overall achievements of the project, discussing future plans for the sustainability of its outcomes, as well as paving the way to scholars in the disciplines to expose their own work on DH&EM in the WBs. This closing event will be held in Tirana towards the end of the project.	UNSA	OTHER	PU	2-Jul-25

2.2 Milestones

Table 2 List of milestones (in chronologic order)

List of milestones					
No	Name	WP No	Lead beneficiary	Means of verification	Due date
1	Approval of Project Management Plan /Board /Tools	WP 1	LOGOS	Document	31 Dec. 2023
8	Development of the Quality Monitoring Action Plan	WP 5	IBC_M	Document	31 Dec. 2023
10	Approval of the Sustainability & Dissemination Plan	WP 6	SSST	Document: terms of reference	31 Jan. 2024
9	Subcontracting the External Expert (Auditor)	WP 5	LOGOS	Document	31 Jan. 2024
6	Procedures under way for establishing Digital Humanities and Educational Media laboratories	WP 4	SEEU	Documents	31 July 2024
5	Preparations for study visits of students	WP 3	LOGOS	Documents	30 Nov. 2024
2	New program and enhanced curricula	WP 2	U_POLIS	Document – draft programme & communication with respect of MoE, where this is necessary	28 Feb. 2025
7	Initiation of first international cooperation agreements.	WP 4	SEEU	Document	31 Aug. 2025
4	Preparations for study visits of academic staff	WP 3	LOGOS	Document	31 Oct. 2025
3	Template of the 12 MOOCs to be developed	WP 2	U_POLIS	Template design and draft content for at least one MOOC to be used as a model.	28 Feb. 2025

3. Homo Digitalis Project Management Strategy and Structures

3.1 Homo Digitalis Project Management Strategy

Homo Digitalis project management strategy is based on a clear distribution of responsibilities among the partners, throughout the 2 years of the project, and on the GA's requirement that "the beneficiaries must have internal arrangements regarding their operation and co-ordination, to ensure that the action is implemented properly" (Chapter 4 Grant Implementation, Section 1 Consortium: Beneficiaries, Affiliated Entities and Other Participants, Article 7 — Beneficiaries). For the effective consortium management and decision-making, a number of structures and mechanisms are created to guarantee efficiency adhering to the principles of delegation, decentralization and control. For a start, the size of the consortium is rather medium and flexible, comprising of experienced and less experienced partners in projects of the sort. Within the spirit of delegation, the leadership in different WPs has been delegated to different partners, in line with their particular strengths.

The main components of the management structure of Homo Digitalis project are:

- 1 The project coordinator
- 2 General Management Committee
- 3 Project Management Committee
- 4 Project and Financial Management team
- 5 Work package leaders

3.2 The Project Coordinator

LOGOS, at the role of the coordinator, is to be the intermediary between the partners and the EC. LOGOS, with the Project Coordinator, Assoc. Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumis, is primarily responsible for the administrative and financial elements of the project throughout the project's duration. But, although LOGOS has the leading role in the project, the expectations are that all partners will share proportionally responsibilities and tasks in its management.

The LOGOS project coordinator shall be responsible for:

- Monitoring compliance by the all partners with their obligations
- Keeping the address list contact persons updated and available
- Collecting, reviewing to verify consistency and submitting reports, other deliverables and specific requested documents to EC.
- Responsible for continues reporting at EU project officer and uploading the final version of deliverables to the SyGma page of the project.
- Transmitting documents and information connected with the Project to any other partners concerned
- Administering the financial contribution of the Funding Authority and fulfilling the financial tasks

- Proposals for changes to Annexes of the Grant Agreement, subject to agreement by the Funding Authority.
- Changes to the Consortium Plan.
- Modifications to the Consortium Agreement.

Evolution of the consortium

- Withdrawal of a Party from the consortium and the approval of the settlement on the conditions of the withdrawal.
- Identification of a breach by a Party of its obligations under the Consortium Agreement or the Grant Agreement.
- Declaration of a Party to be a Defaulting Party
- Remedies to be performed by a Defaulting Party

Membership & Its Selection Procedure: Members of the GMC were officially nominated by each partner HEI. The template, that was filled by each partner, for this committee, can be found at the end of this document, Annex 10.4. The template was sent by email, but was available at the shared drive, too, under a folder titled “Decision-Making Structures”. The structure was initialized on Thursday, 02.11.2023, 12.30-14.00 (GMT +1), when the members of the Homo Digitalis project were invited to attend a first initialization joint meeting of the PMC group together with the GMC group.

Table 5 Homo Digitalis Project’s General Management Committee Membership

No	Organization	Assigned representatives
1	LOGOS University College	1. Assoc. Prof. Konstantinos GIAKOUMIS / Chair 2. Esmeralda Kadena / Member / esmeralda.kadena@kulogos.edu.al
2	Universiteti POLIS shpk	3. Flora Krasniqi / Member / flora_krasniqi@universitetipolis.edu.al 4. Paola Iljazi / Member / paola_iljazi@universitetipolis.edu 5. Malvina Istrefaj / Member / malvina_istrefaj@universitetipolis.edu.al
3	International Business College – Mitrovica	6. Bujar Gallopeni / Member / b.gallopeni@ibcmirovica.eu 7. Damir Gashi / Member / d.gashi@ibcmirovica.eu
4	AAB College	8. Ph.D. (cand.) Ilirjana Geci / Member / ilirjana.geci@universitetiaab.com 9. Assoc. Prof. Arbërore Bicaj / Member / arberore.bicaj@universitetiaab.com
5	University of Sarajevo	10. Selma Rizvic / Member / srizvic@etf.unsa.ba 11. Xx / Member
6	Sarajevo School of Science & Technology	12. Assoc. Prof. Maja Savić-Bojanić / Member 13. Dr. Adnan Huskić / Member / adnan.huskic@ssst.edu.ba
7	South-East European University	14. Lejla Abazi-Bexheti / Member / l.abazi@seeu.edu.mk 15. Arbana Kadriu / Member / a.kadriu@seeu.edu.mk
8	Otto-von-Guericke-Universität	16. Ernesto De Luca / Member / ernesto.deluca@ovgu.de 17. Erasmo Purificato / Member / erasmo.purificato@ovgu.de
9	University of Patra	18. Nikolaos Avouris / Member / avouris@upatras.gr 19. Athanasios Karalis / Member / karalis@upatras.gr
10	Leibniz-Institut Fur Bildungsmedien Georg-Eckert-Inst	N/A

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3.4 Project Management Committee (PMC)

The Project Coordinator is supported by a Project Management Committee who will take responsibility for the day-to-day project management and its financial aspects. The PMC shall meet on an as-needed basis, but with a frequency of no less than twice per project year to steer up the project. This committee will also be in charge of developing the mid-term and final management reports of the project to be debated, finalized and validated by the GMC.

- In the course of the Kick-Off meeting (Tirana, Albania), the PMC will draft a ‘day-to-day’ management strategy accompanied by the Project Management Plan with its communication and reporting components.
- In its second meeting, the PMC will deal with the preparation of the mid-term report of the strategy’s monitoring to EACEA, as well as the validation of the various outcomes and activities of the project’s first half. The Mid-Term Project Management Report to be submitted to EACEA aimed at informing all interested stakeholders about the project’s state-of-the-art (achievements, future steps and main needs/issues to be considered for the following phases of implementation).
- The last PMC meeting will report on the Homo Digitalis project’s results in rapport with its objectives, the development of the project’s final report to EACEA and the crafting of the project’s sustainable outcomes.

PMC is responsible for:

- the coordination of the network.
- collating and reporting project progress to the GMC.
- raising any concerns, risks or issues to the coordinator.
- preparing the agenda for the GMC for approval by the project coordinator and GMC respectively.
- supporting the GMC to ensure that the project aligns with its objectives.
- ensuring the quality of the project and monitoring progress and timelines.
- the effective use of the budget and timely deliveries.
- advising the GMC on ways to rearrange tasks and budgets.
- preparing the mid-term and final project reports to be discussed and validated by the GMC and the Project Coordinator.

Membership & Its Selection Procedure: Members of the PMC were officially nominated by each partner HEI. The template, that was filled by each partner, for this committee, can be found at the end of this document, in Annex 10.4. The template was send by email, but was available at the shared drive, too, under a folder titled “Decision-Making Structures”.

The structure was initialized on Thursday, 02.11.2023, 12.30-14.00 (GMT +1), when the members of the Homo Digitalis Project were invited to attend a first initialization joint meeting of the PMC group together with the GMC group.

Table 6 Homo Digitalis Project Management Committee (PMC)

No	Institution	Assigned representatives
BE 001	LOGOS University College	1. Dr. Valbona Nathanaili / Chair
BE 002	Universiteti POLIS shpk	2. Flora Krasniqi / Member /
BE 003	International Business College - Mitrovica	3. Bujar Gallopeni / Member
BE 004	AAB College	4. Assoc. Prof. Arbërore Bicaj / Member
BE 005	University of Sarajevo	5. Selma Rizvic / Member
BE 006	Sarajevo School of Science & Technology	6. Assoc. Prof. Maja Savić-Bojanić / Member
BE 007	South-East European University	7. Lejla Abazi / Member
BE 008	Otto-von-Guericke-Universitaet	8. Ernesto De Luca / Member
BE 009	University of Patra	9. Nikolaos Avouris /Member, avouris@upatras.gr
BE 010	Leibniz-Institut Fur Bildungsmedien Georg-Eckert-Inst	N/A

3.5 Project and Financial Management Team of Lead Partner

The Project Management Team carries out the day-to-day project management activities for the coordinator including financial issues, project monitoring and organizational and administrative matters.

Table 7 Homo Digitalis Project and Financial Management team

No	Role	Assigned representatives	Organization
1	Project coordinator	Assoc. Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumis	LOGOS
2	Project manager	Dr. Valbona Nathanaili	LOGOS
3	Team member	Adv. Naum (Venian) Mile	LOGOS
4	Team member	McS. Afërdita Pashko	LOGOS

3.6 The Work Package Leaders (WPLs)

Each work package will have a work group of representatives from each partner institution working on the particular activities of the package, under the leadership of one particular HEL, leading the implementation of each of the project's WPs.

Work package leaders are responsible to manage the work and coordination of tasks within their work package. The work package leader role includes:

- Ensuring that the tasks and deliverables within their work package are delivered on time, up to the required quality standards and in accordance to the respective budgetary allocations.
- Identifying and reporting risks and deviations within their work package to the Project Executive, the Project Coordinator and Project Manager.

- Implementing the decisions made at the higher decision-making structures and monitor this part of progress, including day-to-day project management and administration of each activity.

Table 8 Work Package Leaders (WPLs) & Assigned WPL Representatives

No	Work Package (WP) / name	Assigned representative
1	WP 1 Project Management & Coordination (LOGOS)	Assoc. Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumis
2	WP 2 Curriculum Development (U_POLIS)	Malvina Istrefaj / malvina_istrefaj@universitetipolis.edu.al
3	WP 3 Development of academic staff & student learning competencies (UPatra)	Athanasios Karalis / karalis@upatras.gr
4	WP 4 Development of Digital Humanities and Educational Media Laboratories (SEEU)	Lejla Abazi / l.abazi@seeu.edu.mk
5	WP 5 Quality Assurance (IBC-M)	Gresa Ferri / g.ferri@ibcmirovica.eu
6	WP 6: Dissemination & exploitation (SSST)	Emina Vejsilović / emina.vejsilovic@ssst.edu.ba

Graph 1 Homo Digitalis Project Management Structures

3.7 Consortium members' /contacts persons

Table 9 Consortium members' /contacts persons

No.	Participant organization name	Partner's abbreviation	Country	Contacts
1	LOGOS University College	LOGOS	Albania	1. Assoc. Prof. Konstantinos Giakoumis, konstantinos.giakoumis@kulogos.edu.al 2. Dr. Valbona Nathanaili, valbona.nathanaili@kulogos.edu.al
2	POLIS University	U_POLIS		1. Dr. Flora Krasniqi, flora_krasniqi@universitetipolis.edu.al 2. Dr. Elona Karafili, elona_karafili@universitetipolis.edu.al
3	International Business College Mitrovica	IBC_M	Kosovo*	1. Mihone Kerolli Mustafa, m.kerolli@ibcmirovica.eu 2. Gresa Ferri, g.ferri@ibcmirovica.eu
4	Kolegji AAB	EDU invest		1. Arberore Bicaj, arberore.bicaj@universitetiaab.com 2. Qendresa Kukaj, qendresa.kukaj@universitetiaab.com
5	Univerzitet U Sarajevu	UNSA	Bosna i Hercegovina	1. Selma Rizvic, srizvic@etf.unsa.ba 2. Renato Scuzzarello, renatoscuzzarello@libero.it
6	Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola Za Nauku i Tehnologiju PU	SSST		1. Maja Savic-Bojanic, maja.savic@ssst.edu.ba
7	South East European University Tetovo	SEEU	North Macedonia	1. Lejla Abazi, l.abazi@seeu.edu.mk 2. Irena Gjerasimovska, i.gjerasimovska@seeu.edu.mk 3. Arbana Kadriu, a.kadriu@seeu.edu.mk
8	Otto-Von-Guericke-Universitaet Magdeburg	OVGU	Germany	1. Ernesto-William De Luca, ernesto.deluca@ovgu.de 2. Veronica Kauert, veronika.kauert@ovgu.de
9	Panepistimio Patron	UPatra	Greece	1. Thanasis Karalis, karalis@upatras.gr 2. Nikolaos Avouris, navouris@gmail.com
10	Leibniz-Institut Fur Bildungsmedien Georg-Eckert-Institut	GEI	Germany	1. Kerstin Matthes, kerstin.matthes@ovgu.de

3.8 Homo Digitalis Project Partner Information

HOMO DIGITALIS has 9 (nine) partners (consortium members) led by LOGOS University College, from 6 (six) countries.

Three Non-EU Partner Countries are involved:

1. Albania, with 2 HEIs: LOGOS University College and POLIS University (located in Tirana).
2. Bosnia and Herzegovina, with 2 HEIs: Univerzitet u Sarajevu (UNSA) and Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola za Nauku i Tehnologiju PU (SSST) (located in Sarajevo)
3. Kosovo* with 2 HEIs: International Business College – Mitrovica (IBC_M) and Kolegji AAB (EDU Invest shpk) (the first one, located in Mitrovica and the second one in Pristina).

Two Programme Countries are involved:

4. Greece, with 1 HEI: Panepistimio Patron (UPatra) (located in Patras).

5. Project’s commitment for using green practices

The following measures will be considered, to develop digital transformation of practices and all network:

- use of eco - friendly and energy - efficient equipment and technologies by choosing products with recognized environmental certifications
- virtual meetings, webinars, and online collaboration platforms to reduce the need for travel and minimize carbon emissions digital documentation
- communication methods to reduce paper usage sharing project updates, resources, and reports electronically
- use of energy-efficient devices using of recyclable materials for any physical products, packaging, or promotional materials
- use of digital educational materials encouraging the use of e-books, online articles, and interactive learning platform

6. Organizational meetings and procedures

6.1 Frequency of Consortium Meetings

Regular project management will be guaranteed by three GMC meetings, at the start, the middle and the end of the project.

Table 10 Frequency of Consortium Meetings

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Management Committee (GMC)	At least once a year / every 9 months <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4-6 December 2023, kick off meeting • the middle (on line meeting) • end of the project 	At any time upon written request of the Project Coordinator or 1/3 of the Members. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • First extraordinary meeting was online, on Thursday, 02.11.2023, 12.30-14.00 (GMT +1) MS TEAMS (see report of kick off meeting)
Project Management Committee (PMC)	At least 4 semi-annual meetings <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 4-6 December 2023, kick off meeting • June, 2024 (on line meeting) • February, 2025 (on line meeting) • end of the project 	First initialization meeting was online, on Thursday, 02.11.2023, 12.30-14.00 (GMT +1) MS TEAMS (see report of kick off meeting)

6.2 Notice of a meeting

Table 11 Notice of a meeting

	Ordinary meeting	Extraordinary meeting
General Management (Steering) Committee (GMC)	Written notification, at least a month before the meeting, after selection of most convenient date and time.	Written notification, ideally at least a week before the meeting, after selection of most convenient date and time.
Project Management Committee (PMC)	Written notification, at least a month before the meeting, after selection of most convenient date and time.	Written notification, ideally at least a week before the meeting, after selection of most convenient date and time.

6.3 Sharing the agenda

PMC shall prepare a first version of the written agenda no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below. The Project Manager shall send each Member of General Management Committee (GMC).

Table 12 Sending the agenda

General Management (Steering) Committee (GMC)	21 calendar days, 10 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Committee (PMC)	7 calendar days

6.4 Adding agenda items

Any agenda item requiring a decision by the GMC must be designated as such in the agenda. Any Member of GMC may add an item to the original agenda by written notification to all of the other members of a particular decision-making structure no later than the minimum number of days preceding the meeting as indicated below.

Table 13 Adding agenda items

General Management (Steering) Committee (GMC)	14 calendar days, 7 calendar days for an extraordinary meeting
Project Management Committee (PMC)	2 calendar days

6.5 Files and document templates

All project related files will be stored in the tool's online repository following the process which will be described in the project quality plan. The versioning of files is automatically taken care of by the tool and all newer versions of the same file are automatically recorded as the latest version while previous ones can be invoked by the users.

The history of a version is also tracked by the tool and can be also invoked. The MS Project tool will also be utilized to track project progress against the work plan and the consumption of resources at task, work package and project level. Document templates shall be produced providing a standard format including defined styles, page layout, content structure, logos and disclaimer text. These templates must be approved by the Project WP 5 Quality Assurance Team and are available as Appendixes (10. 3) under General Documents/Templates.

Templates have been produced for:

- Deliverables (MS Word format)
- Sign Up Sheet (MS Word format)

All official project documents should use these templates.

6.6 Acknowledgment to EU Funding: Visibility & Quality of information — Disclaimer

All communication activities of the beneficiaries related to the action (including media relations, conferences, seminars, information material, such as brochures, leaflets, posters, presentations, etc., in electronic form, via traditional or social media, etc.), dissemination activities and any infrastructure, equipment, vehicles, supplies or major result funded by the grant must acknowledge the EU support and display the European flag (emblem) and funding statement (GA, Article 17.2).

Any communication or dissemination activity related to the action must use factually accurate information. Moreover, it must indicate the following disclaimer (translated into local languages where appropriate) (GA, Article 17.3, Quality of information — Disclaimer):

“Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or [name of the granting authority]. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

7. Project communication strategy

This section determines the project’s communication strategy for all what regards WP 1 communication needs. A Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy is a document to be developed under WP 6 that sets forth the ways in which the project’s outputs are to be communicated to the targeted outreach in a clear and measurable way.

In this regard, this document is to be read and implemented in conjunction with provisions laid out in the said Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy document.

7.1 Internal Communication

7.1.1 Language of Communications

The official language of the project is English. Hence, all types of communications and reach-out activities are to be held in English, especially when they involve target groups not sharing the same language.

This principle is not applicable when communications are directed to local state authorities, or in cases when specific messages need to reach out underprivileged people, for whom language might be a barrier from participating in international credit mobility. In these cases, as well as others, when this is deemed appropriate, a local West Balkan language may be used.

7.1.2 Contact lists

Upon institutional consent, a contact list of institutional e-mail addresses has been created and distributed to all partners. The contact list is available in an MS Excel worksheet and is maintained by the Project Manager. The contact list also includes the contact details of other persons for alternative forms of communication. The contact list breaks down the work packages for which each contact wishes to receive communication.

7.1.3 Personal Data Usage Consent Form

‘Homo Digitalis’ Project involves close collaboration and necessitates efficient communication and coordination among academic and administrative staff. To achieve the project's objectives, the experience is that using personal phone numbers may be necessary, as it will enable to promptly communicate important updates, share critical information, and coordinate project-related activities effectively. The consent is to collect and use personal phone numbers of different project staff during the lifetime of the project “Homo Digitalis as required by GDPR and to only use these phone numbers for project-related communications, without share them with external parties (see Appendix 10.2, Personal Data Usage Consent Form: “Homo Digitalis” Project).

Every person whose name is listed in any document of the drive's “Communications” folder was kindly requested to send the statement “Personal Data Usage Consent Form” signed.

7.1.4 E-mail

Email is expected to be the primary form of communication within the HD project. For ease of identifying HD relevant e-mails, we recommend that all email subjects should begin with “HOMO DIGITALIS”.

7.1.5 Meetings

Meetings can be held in-person, online (via teleconference), or a combination thereof. While face-to-face meetings are preferred on account of the lateral benefits they bring, budgetary limitations, green issues’ considerations, time restrictions or the unavailability of some staff pushes for hybrid or online meetings. Partner HEIs coordinating discussions in a hybrid or online mode should use their own institutional tools and resources to guarantee that such communications are always as efficient as face-to-face communications.

Minutes of meeting on line and in person will use the template of appendix 10.1.

7.1.6 Videoconferencing (for example TEAMS or Skype)

Videoconferencing is recommended as a means of green and cost-effective communication and an alternative to short in-person meetings. The most effective videoconferencing is one that is well structured, taking place after the group has already met so that it can recognize the speaker. The aims and objectives of each meeting should be clear from the outset. Videoconferencing is especially useful for:

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- Group deliberations on a document or presentation.
- Briefly discussing technical or management issues.
- Assigning tasks to participants.
- Making decisions requiring urgent actions.
- Whenever a certain important issue needs to be discussed in between meetings and a prompt reaction by consortium members is required

To ensure that videoconferences are as efficient as possible, it is recommended that:

- The meeting is limited to a small group of participants.
- Documents and agendas should be shared ahead of the meeting so that attendees know what the meeting is about, can securely access the meeting and be prepared when it starts.
- The meeting has a clear aim and objective and, where possible, limits the meeting to individuals presenting or reporting back to the group, confirming that they will take future actions or agreeing on predefined points.
- Videoconferencing should be minuted and organized in the same way as any other meetings, with an agenda issued prior to the meeting, a list of participants recorded as well as a list of actions produced.

To track record of deliberations and decisions, teleconference meetings of hybrid meetings can be recorded. To address any potential personal data protection issues, however, such meetings could be recorded only upon the informed consent of all participants.

7.2 Web: www.adminproject.eu

The project management shall use a project management and collaboration platform which serves the complete project life cycle (www.adminproject.eu). The process to be used is one tool/medium for everything pertinent to the project. Initially a dedicated project space for the project will be created inside the project management platform. Then, the structure of the online file repository will be created following an ISO-like structure.

The admin project will be used for facilitating the day-to-day operational management by providing a task-based system allowing the creation and assignment to the project team of tasks in response to the work plan tasks and activities.

7.3 External Communication

By external communication we define the process of reaching out to diverse external audience groups (including but not limited to academics, administrative staff, students beyond the consortium HEIs, organisations, Ministries or other third parties) for the purpose of communicating various aspects related to the project.

The media to be used in the context of external communications are the same as the media to be used in internal communications. For details, reference is made to the project's Dissemination & Exploitation Strategy.

8. Financial management

This section aims to give orientations and clarifications for the financial aspects of the project. To provide maximal accuracy, the rules and orientations written below are based and most of them are taken from the EU Commission guidelines for the use of the grant agreement (GA).

All transfers to project beneficiaries are made via bank transfers and that all the bank statements are kept with the project accounts.

8.1. Lump sum, Co-financing and no-profit

The funding rule under this call is in the form of a single fixed amount (lump sum), covering all costs of eligible activities linked to the implementation of the project. Lump sum payments are subject to the implementation of the triggering event, that is to say the completion of the action. LOGOS, as the beneficiary of the grant, has no obligation to provide evidence of the actual costs incurred upon the project's completion.

However, LOGOS will report project achievements. It should be borne in mind that, should these achievements be found in any way substandard, the Agency may apply grant reductions to ensure that the grant remains proportional to the quality of the activities implemented by the project.

As in all grants funded by the European Union budget, contributions in the context of this action shall comply with the principles of co-financing and no-profit. The principle of co-financing implies that the resources necessary to carry out the action are not provided entirely by the grant. Co-financing may be provided in the form of the beneficiary's own resources, income generated by the action or financial or in-kind contributions from third parties. In line with the no-profit principle, Grants shall not have the purpose or effect of producing a profit within the framework of the action or the work programme of the beneficiary.

8.2. Budget management

LOGOS and other WP leaders shall enjoy flexibility in the management of the budget allocated to each work package. However, at the reporting stage, the amount paid for each work package should always correspond to budgetary provisions allocated at the GA and Detailed Budget, and depend on the level of achievement of the objectives of the work package.

In case that, during the implementation of the project, a WPL needs to modify the budget allocated to the work package and the related list of activities, this can be done by requesting an amendment at GMC. If the amendment is approved by this first organism, the same request will be assessed by the EACEA and, if approved by the second one too, it becomes part of the grant agreement.

8.3. Summary of the budget

The budget for management (WP1), including risk management, takes up 17.23% of the overall requested fund. WP2 and WP3 take up 16.98% and 16.77% of the project respectively; WP4 take 28.42%. The HD project will also deploy sophisticated Quality Assurance Work (WP5). Evaluation activities have a budget of close to 44,685 € corresponding to about 11.24% of the project budget. The budget for WP6 (Exploitation & Dissemination) is at a rate of 9.36 %; the project has been drafted counting on considerable institutional support beyond this rate.

Table 14. Summary of the budget, for each partner, according to WPs (BE + AE Total Cost)

No.	Partner's name and abbreviation	WP 1 Project Management & Coordination	WP 2 Curriculum Development	WP 3 Development of academic staff & student learning competencies	WP 4 Development of DH&EM Laboratories	WP 5 Quality Assurance	WP 6 Dissemination & exploitation
1	LOGOS University College (LOGOS)	15,793 €	10,458 €	11,007 €	25,038 €*	12,808 €	12,365 €
2	Univerziteti Poljski (U_POLIS)	5,200 €	12,095 €	11,681 €	21,860 €*	4,333 €	6,298 €
3	International Business College Mitrovica (IBC-M)	5,168 €	6,895 €	7,444 €	16,178 €*	3,756 €	3,205 €
4	Kolegij AAB	4,776 €	6,259 €	7,781 €	12,028 €*	1,300 €	3,205 €
5	Univerzitet u Sarajevu (UNSA)	7,893 €	8,858 €	6,288 €	10,096 €*	3,306 €	4,168 €
6	Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola za Nauku&Tehnologiju PU (SSST)	6,631 €	6,276 €	6,982 €	10,975 €*	2,330 €	3,365 €
7	Otto-Von-Guericke-Universitaet Magdeburg (OVGU)	7,653 €	7,653 €	6,259 €	6,259 €	6,259 €	0 €
8	Panepistimio Patron (UPatra)	11,006 €	4,315 €	5,970 €	5,970 €	5,970 €	2,985 €
9	South East European University Tetovo (SEEU)	4,397 €	4,721 €	3,274 €	4,622 €	4,622 €	1,637 €
10	GEI	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	€ 68,518 €	€ 67,530 €	€ 66,687 €	€ 113,026 €	€ 44,685 €	€ 37,228 €

Note 1: *value approved, as a GA amendment – also, see table below.

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HD: WP4 Development of Digital Humanities and Educational Media Laboratories / C2: Equipment

	HEI	Budget: TPL /C2 Equipment	Proposed change (- 12%)	New Budget	New Max BE Contribution
BE001	LOGOS	20,000.00 €	2,400.00 €	17,600.00 €	15,840.00 €
BE002	UPolis	17,500.00 €	2,100.00 €	15,400.00 €	13,860.00 €
BE003	IBC_M	15,000.00 €	1,800.00 €	13,200.00 €	11,880.00 €
BE004	AAB	10,500.00 €	1,260.00 €	9,240.00 €	8,316.00 €
BE005	University of Sarajevo	0.00 €	0.00 €	8,784.00 €	7,905.60 €
BE006	SSST	10,200.00 €	1,224.00 €	8,976.00 €	8,078.40 €

8.4. Payments from the European Commission

The maximum EC financial contribution for the HOMO DIGITALIS project has been fixed at € 397,675.00. The EC has already made a pre-financing payment 70% of the aforementioned lump-sum (€ 278,372.5), which has been proportionately distributed by the Lead Partner to the consortium partners, equal to 5/7 (total: € 198,837.5).

Table 15 Payments from EC to LOGOS and from LOGOS to partners

N o.	Partner's name and abbreviation	EU Total Contribution (A)	First EU Contribution = 70% of A (10/2023, to LOGOS) (B)	First instalment, from LOGOS, lead beneficiary, to partners (11/2023) (C)	Second instalment, from LOGOS, lead beneficiary, to partners (D=B-C)	Final payment of the EU contribution = 30% of A (E)
1	LOGOS University College (LOGOS)	87,469 €*	61,228.3 €*	44,890 €	16,338.30 €*	26,240.70 €*
2	Universteti Poljs (U_POLIS)	61,468 €*	43,027.6 €*	31,745 €	11,282.60 €*	18,440.40 €*
3	International Business College Mitrovica IBC-M	42,646 €*	29,852.2 €*	22,189.5 €	7,662.70 €*	12,793.80 €*
4	Kolegij AAB	35,350 €*	24,745 €*	18,282 €	6,463.00 €*	10,605.00 €*
5	Univerzitet u Sarajevu (UNSA)	40,609 €*	28,426.3 €*	16,074.5 €	12,351.80 €*	12,182.70 €*
6	Univerzitet-Sarajevska Skola za Nauku i Tehnologiju PU(SSST)	36,560 €*	25,592 €*	18,868.5 €	6,723.50 €*	10,968.00 €*
7	Otto-Von-Guericke-Universitaet Magdeburg (OVGU)	34,085 €	23,859.5 €	17,042.5 €	6,817.00 €	10,225.50 €
8	Panepistimio Patron (UPatra)	36,217 €	25,351.9 €	18,108.5 €	7,243.40 €	10,865.10 €
9	South East European University Tetovo SEEU	23,274 €	16,291.8 €	11,637 €	4,654.80 €	6,982.20 €
10	GEI	0	0	0	0	0
	Total	397,675.00 €	€ 278,372.5	198,837.5 €	79,537.10 €	119,303.40 €

Note 1: Please note that, according to Article 22, Point 1 of the Grant Agreement, “the beneficiary bears the cost of transfers charged by its bank”. The calculations above are contingent upon the resolutions to address some glitches to be detailed in Item No. 6 of the meeting's agenda.

Note 2: *value is approved, as a GA amendment.

The final payment, equal with 30% of the requested EU contribution, for each partner, will be made in accordance to rules and conditions specified in the GA at the time indicated therein.

9. Project risk management

The risk management process consists of 5 key steps:

1. Identify and assess risk
2. Analyse critical risks
3. Development of contingency plans
4. Implement contingency plans
5. Update risk register and follow up of contingency plans

A list of risks was identified during the grant preparation stage and reviewed at the kick-off meeting.

Table 16 Risk register and mitigation measures

Risk No	Description	WP No	Proposed Mitigation Measures	Data added to risk register
R1	The Lead Partner is institutionally rather inexperienced in PM / low	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	The project's lead partner has now built some experience in project writing and management, as a result of successful ERASMUS+ CBHE project applications of last year's call. In addition, the consortium was set up in such a way, as to guarantee a combination of experienced and inexperienced institutions, the latter being among the target groups of this year's CBHE projects, in order to help the latter group, acquire the necessary experience	Proposal writing stage
R2	Lack of overall coordination	WP1	Effective coordination is ensured by the managerial structure and through the project work plan. In case of unforeseen events, other experienced persons at the coordinating institute or at other partners can take over coordination tasks	Proposal writing stage
R3	Lack of engagement	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	The risk is low, since all partners have previous experience in RTD projects while on the other hand they note their strong interest in establishing new and revised courses and extend their academic activities in the DH. If a partner proves unable to fulfil the obligations within its role, the impact on the whole project will not be crucial, since the main consequences will be related to the relevant HEI	Proposal writing stage
R4	Conflicts in the Consortium.	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	A comprehensive CA will be formulated by all partners. The coordinator will follow strict administrative guidelines and implement actions against partners failing to comply with procedures agreed upon in the CA. If this is insufficient, then, Mediation and positive approach to disputes resolution will be sought.	Proposal writing stage

R5	Selected methods are shown to be inadequate or not fully appropriate	WP3, WP2, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	The methodological design will be modified in a grounded fashion in the process. Planned intervention methods will be modified to fully correspond with the properties& needs of the project's target groups.	Proposal writing stage
R6	Delays in deliverables.	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	A timely delivery is essential and all consortium partners are dedicated to the timeline. Consortium members will be consulted and informed of the project timeline. Strict and continuous monitoring of deadlines in the project management will help mitigate the risk of falling behind schedule.	Proposal writing stage
R7	Different academic cultures, rules and regulations	WP2, WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	This is a regional and cross-regional project that may face various administrative, and management challenges due to different educational cultures, rules and regulations applicable in the different countries of the consortium. The risk that these differences may have a negative impact on the project is low, not only because all partner HEIs adhere to the Bologna process, but also because they have a firm understanding of the benefits of the project objectives	Proposal writing stage
R8	There are public and private HEIs from the West Balkans in the consortium and, depending on national tax legislation, they may get different treatment with regard to the reimbursement of the value added tax.	WP1	The VAT costs for the private HEIs will be covered by the very private HEIs' own resources	Proposal writing stage
R9	Institutional disagreements in curriculum development	WP2	Due diligence consultations have been made ahead of the application phase. Consultations with well experienced European universities will be solicited to identify resolutions to bypass any curriculum development hardship.	Proposal writing stage
R10	Disapproval of new or updated curricula by the competent Ministry authorities	WP2	It should be noted that for most curriculum development procedures are within the limits of academic autonomy, thereby not necessitating Ministry approvals. In recognition of the role of digital transformation for sustainable growth and jobs, competent Ministries for HE in the WB have set these as overarching objectives, thereby guaranteeing political backing in cases of new study programmes development whenever Ministry approvals are required. QA mechanisms promise to deliver the required quality of project applications. In the rather unlikely case that a new study programme is not approved, focus will be switched to an increased number of courses to be revised/ updated.	Proposal writing stage
R11	Difficulties in recruiting new, qualified staff to deliver the new or updated courses.	WP2	Sufficient funding has been allocated for staff costs, as well as the learning and training enhancement of existing academic staff to deliver these courses. As a last resort, expertise will be solicited from qualified staff from the pool of consortium partners	Proposal writing stage
R12	Low number of students in new study programmes	WP2	Proper promotion of the project and the very study programme shall mitigate this risk. Tuition fee incentives will also be set, as lab investment is to be made with project funds	Proposal writing stage
R13	Academic, administrative staff and students' resistance to learn new methods & practices; or to change & learn new ways of operation.	WP2, WP3, WP4	Development of appropriate group dynamics to isolate phenomena of resistance or procrastination.	Proposal writing stage
R14	Loss of critical	WP2,	Each expert group in the project is composed of a number of	Proposal

	competencies or key people in the project	WP3, WP5, WP1, WP4, WP6	participants with a similar level of expertise, so the role of the withdrawn participant can be taken over by one of the remaining participants.	writing stage
R15	Targeted groups: students with disabilities, students from lower socio-economic strata - are nervous, afraid or not interested in the project's opportunities	WP2, WP3	Set of tools to communicate with targeted groups will be enlarged and improved to make project results more attractive	Proposal writing stage
R16	Some training sessions may require more time than planned.	WP3	The team will adapt the training work in other training sessions and / or use technology to facilitate communications between the trainer and the trainees beyond the planned face-to-face trainings.	Proposal writing stage
R17	Delays in the procurement of equipment & Lab development.	WP4	As there is no high-tech equipment required for the implementation of this project, existent infrastructure will be temporarily be used for the needs of the project. In addition, the start date of WP-4 will be set rather early in the project's lifetime.	Proposal writing stage
R18	Difficulties with subcontractors	WP5, WP6	The partner in charge of subcontracting experts will launch an international call for experts from the ranks of individuals, as well as companies	Proposal writing stage
R19	Subcontracting costs may increase during the lifespan of the project compared to the actual forecast.	WP5, WP6	Subcontracted services will be prioritized and negotiation of the financial terms of the contracts will be conducted since the first year of the project	Proposal writing stage
R20	Staff in charge of Quality Assurance Monitoring being unavailable	WP5	Alternative human resources will be used for the conduct of the foreseen quality monitoring work.	Proposal writing stage
R21	Low standards of QMAP, internal & external QM reports.	WP5	The quality of the project's outputs will be set in advance by a QMAP, monitored by a QMC audited by an external QA expert. The presence of more experienced partners in the consortium also mitigates this risk	Proposal writing stage
R22	Lack of public/market awareness of Project activities	WP5	Dissemination activities and contacts with other bodies and institutions in the area, relevant project consortia, stakeholders and market players (chambers, companies etc.) will be intensified to counteract situation.	Proposal writing stage

A risk management strategy is required to ensure that the impact from any negative deviation from the Description of Action is minimised. There are four well-known approaches to mitigate and respond to risk (In case of low impact, the Accept or Avoid approach is applicable. In all cases, an action will be required and will be documented).

1. Avoid - by eliminating the thread we also eliminate the risk.
2. Mitigate - A plans to find ways to reduce the probability of the occurrence of the thread.
3. Accept - The impact of the risk is very low or there is nothing to be done.
4. Transfer - We transfer the responsibility of managing the thread to a third party.

From the Table 15, most of the project risks are of a low level and all of them are identifying during the Proposal Writing Stage. During the same stage, for each of them is compiled a plan to recover. PMC will be responsible for identifying if the solution to mitigate and control the impact is correct. Each risk will be assessed for its criticality to the overall plan of work and normal risk assessment techniques such as a likelihood/severity matrix can be used for assessing the potential

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risk impact and therefore the requirement for the implementation of a contingency plan. Any contingency plan developed and implemented as a result of the risk management process will be subject to reporting and periodic progress updates to the project management team and to the GMC.

10. APPENDIXES

10.1 APPENDIX – Minutes meeting: first meeting on line

This form will be used for all meetings, on line and in presence.

Thursday, 02.11.2023, 12.30-14.00 (GMT +1)

MS TEAMS

PROJECT MEETING No. 1

AGENDA

Minutes Meeting

Members:

	University	First Name	Last Name	First Name	Last Name
1	LOGOS University College	Konstantinos	Giakomis	Valbona	Nathanaili
2	POLIS University	Flora	Krasniqi	Elona	Karafili
3	University of Sarajevo	Selma	Rizvic	Renato	Scuzzarello
4	University Sarajevo School of Science & Technology	Jasmina	Bajramović-Malić		
5	International Business College, Mitrovica	Mihone	Kerrolli Mustafa	Gresa	Ferri
6	AAB College	Qendresa	Kukaj		
7	University of Patras	Thanasis	Karalis	Nikolaos	Avouris
8	South-East European University	Lejla	Abazi		
9	Otto-von-Guericke University of Magdeburg	Ernesto-William	De Luca	Veronica	Kauert
10	Georg Eckert Institute (associated partner)	Ernesto-William	De Luca		

Invitees: Members of the Project Management Committee

Extraordinary Participation: -

On Thursday, 02.11.2023 at 12.30 (GMT +1), the founding members of the Homo Digitalis project are invited to attend a first, project-initialization meeting. The meeting's agenda items are as follows:

ITEMS FOR DISCUSSION		Presenter
1	Informed consent for the recording of the meeting.	KG
<u>Deliberations & Decisions:</u> Informed consent was provided orally and in writing (cf. link)		
2	Introduction to each other.	All
<u>Deliberations & Decisions:</u> N/A		
3	Pre-Financing Transfer Forms: 3.1 <u>Pre-Financing Sums:</u> Pre-Financing Instalment per partner (Homo Digitalis).xlsx . 3.2 <u>Bank Account Specifications:</u> Bank Account Specs.docx 3.3 <u>Pre-Financing Payment Request:</u> Pre-Financing Payment Request.docx	KG
<u>Deliberations & Decisions:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Participants were cautioned to anticipate their pre-financing payment in conjunction to decisions to be made as per Discussion Point No. 6. <u>Dead-Line:</u> TBD Partners were kindly requested to send their bank account specifications at their earliest. <u>Dead-Line:</u> 10.11.2023 Partners were kindly requested to fill all of the parts of the pre-financing payment request and wait until decisions will be made on Discussion Point No. 6, after which they will fill the amount and send the form. <u>Dead-Line:</u> TBD 		
4	Partners' Officially Appointed Representatives in...: 4.1 <u>Decision-Making Structures (all-inclusive):</u> Decision-Making Structures' Membership.xlsx 4.2 <u>Partners Representation in the Kick-Off Meeting:</u> Nomination Form.docx . 4.3 <u>In WPs:</u> Partners' WPs Representation.xlsx .	KG
<u>Deliberations & Decisions:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Partners were requested to officially nominate their representation in the project's Decision-Making Structures by filling this form, having it signed and stamped by their competent authorities and filling this Table. <u>Dead-Line:</u> 10.11.2023. Partners were also requested to officially nominate their representation in the project's Kick-Off meeting by filling the relevant section of the form above. <u>Dead-Line:</u> 10.11.2023 		
5	List of Communications' Recipients.	KG
<u>Deliberations & Decisions:</u> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Partner institutions were requested to verify that the list of main contact and contact persons are up to date, by checking and modifying this document. <u>Dead-Line:</u> 10.11.2023. Partner institutions were requested to check the list of e-mail recipients of the project, add to and remove from this list any colleagues from your home institutions as per your authorization. <u>Dead-Line:</u> 10.11.2023. 		
6	GA Glitches and Resolutions: WP-1, WP-4 & WP-6: 6.1 Issue No. 1: In the context of project application and GAP, we omitted to provision any budget for equipment for the University of Sarajevo, although in their queries they had requested a budget ranging from 17,000 to 20,000 €. This is a mistake on our part (the burden is on us, as lead) and we ought to find some way to address is, because enhancing the laboratory infrastructure is amongst the principal objective of CBHE projects. We thought of re-budgeting WP-4 (relevant	KG

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such data, and repealing Regulation (EC) No 45/2001 and Decision No 1247/2002/EC (OJ L 295, 21.11.2018, p. 39).

2. In full compliance with: *Grant Agreement (Article 15) of the mentioned project*

3. In full compliance with: *National law on data protection (in particular, Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC ('GDPR') (OJ L 119, 4.5.2016, p. 1),*

we are committed to ensuring the privacy and security of personal information.

We are seeking your consent before collecting and using our personal phone numbers during the lifetime of the project "Homo Digitalis". We will provide them with clear information about the purpose of collecting their phone numbers and their rights regarding data protection, as required by GDPR. We will only use these phone numbers for project-related communications and will not share them with external parties.

We kindly request your approval for this use of personal phone numbers in the context of the project 'Homo Digitalis', ensuring that it complies fully with above regulation. Please fill the annex of this document (page no.2), and send to valbona.nathanaili@kulogos.edu.al.

If you have any specific requirements or guidelines related to data protection that we should follow, please let us know, and we will ensure full compliance.

Thank you for your consideration of this request.

Signed

1. Name, Last Name
2. Affiliation
3. Institution Name
4. Institution address
5. Personal Phone Number

I approve using of my Personal Phone Number according to this document.

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10.3 APPENDIX: General Documents/Templates

10.3.1. Event attendance form

ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-1

Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the West Balkans
(101129182- HOMO DIGITALIS)

Event:

Venue: / Date: / Starting time:

Partner responsible and coordinator for WP (No.):

Contact e-mail: [.....](#)

No.	First Name	Last Name	Institution	Permission signature ¹	E-mail address	<i>Please, specify:</i> Academic staff (AcC)/ Administrative Staff (AdS) / Student (S) / Other (O)			
						AcC	AdS	S	O
1									
2									
3									
4									
5									
6									
7									
8									
9									
10									
11									
12									
13									
14									

¹ I hereby confirm by my signature that I give my informed consent for project organizers and partners to use event photos for project promotion activities.

ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-1

Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the West Balkans
(101129182- HOMO DIGITALIS)

Training:

Venue: / **Date:** / **Starting time:**

Partner responsible and coordinator for WP (No.):

Contact e-mail:

Last Name	First Name	Institution	Position	Role in the training	Email

10.3.2. Questionnaire 1

On-line surveys (Google form)

Impact analysis of _____ Homo Digitalis Project meeting

As part of the impact report analysis, please answer the questions below according to your opinion about the _____ project meeting. Please tick your favorite answers to the following questions.

Thanks for your cooperation!

1. Did you find the meeting useful? (answer required)

- Very useful
- Useful
- Not very useful
- Not useful at all

Question 1 – additional comments/suggestions:

2. Were the meeting/event objectives clearly stated? (answer required)

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- Satisfied
- Not very satisfied
- Not satisfied at all

Question 5 – additional comments/suggestions:

6. What is your overall satisfaction about the productivity this meeting/event)? (answer required)

- Very productive
- Productive
- Not very productive
- Not productive at all

Question 6 – additional comments/suggestions:

7. What subject areas did you find particularly useful? (answer required)

- _____ (name)

Question 7 – additional comments/suggestions:

8. Further remarks and comments

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10.3.4. Guideline for reporting

Erasmus+ Programme
(ERASMUS-EDU-2023-CBHE-STRAND-1)
Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the
West Balkans
(Project 101129182 — Homo Digitalis)

< Deliverable / Milestone name >

< Deliverable / Milestone code >

[University Name]

Work Package []

Version: [number]

[Date]

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

Partners:

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The preparation of an executive summary report may be short and useful.

Partners:

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DOCUMENT CONTROL

Project acronym:	HOMO DIGITALIS
Project Title:	Bridging the Digital Humanities and Educational Media Divide in the West Balkans
Date:	
Author:	
Reviewer:	
Activity:	
Type:	
Product:	
Dissemination level:	
Filename:	
Pages:	

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

SEN	Sensitive / Restricted to a group specified by the HOMO DIGITALIS
PUB	PUBLIC

TYPE

R	Document, report
DEC	Website/ patent filings, videos, etc.

PRODUCT

D	Deliverable
M	Milestone

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DOCUMENT HISTORY / MODIFICATION RECORD

VERSION	DATE	AUTHOR	Review	Comments/Change Details
0.1				
0.2				
0.3				
0.4				
1.0				

Partners:

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10.4 Appendix: Partners' Nomination Form

Partner's Nomination form of Representatives in Project Management & Quality Structures

Date: __.__.2023

Name of Partner Institution:	
Name, Surname and Position of Nominator:	

1. GENERAL MANAGEMENT

#	Name & Surname of Nominee	Nominee's Contacts Details
1.		
2.		

2. PROJECT MANAGEMENT COMMITTEE

#	Name & Surname of Nominee	Nominee's Contacts Details
1.		

3. QUALITY MONITORING COMMITTEE

#	Name & Surname of Nominee	Nominee's Contacts Details
1.		

4. KICK-OFF MEETING PARTICIPANTS

#	Name & Surname of Nominee	Nominee's Contacts Details
1.		
2.		
3.		
4.		
5.		
6.		
7.		
8.		
9.		

Name, Surname and Signature of Nominator; stamp of the partner institution

10.5 Appendix: Bibliography

Christian Friedl (2016). KTU Project Handbook. Knowledge Transfer Unit - From Applied Research and Technology-Entrepreneurial Know-How Exchange to Development of Interdisciplinary Curricula Modules. Reference Number: 544031-TEMPUS-1-2013-1-AT-TEMPUS-JPHES.

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Paragreen, J. (2015). Deliverable D8.1. Project Management Plan. Needs Tailored Interoperable Railway – NeTIRail-INFRA. Collaborative project H2020-MG-2015-2015 GA-636237.

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10.6 Appendix: Decision, template

Chair, LOGOS		
Dr. Valbona Nathanaili		
Member, Polis University	Member, International Business College - Mitrovica	Member, AAB College
Flora Krasniqi	Bujar Gallopeni	Assoc. Prof. Arbërore Bicaj
Member, University of Sarajevo	Member, Sarajevo School of Science & Technology	Member, South-East European University
Selma Rizvic	Assoc. Prof. Maja Savić-Bojanić	Lejla Abazi
Member, Otto-von-Guericke-Universitaet	Member, University of Patra	
Ernesto De Luca	Nikolaos Avouris	

December, __, 2023

Decision

Members

1. Dr. Valbona Nathanaili, Chair, LOGOS, University College /
2. Flora Krasniqi, member, Polis University
3. Bujar Gallopeni, Member, International Business College, Mitrovica
4. Assoc. Prof. Arbërore Bicaj, Member, AAB College
5. Selma Rizvic, University of Sarajevo
6. Assoc. Prof. Maja Savić-Bojanić, member, Sarajevo School of Science & Technology
7. Lejla Abazi, member, South-East European University
8. Ernesto De Luca, member, Otto-von-Guericke-Universitaet
9. Nikolaos Avouris, member, University of Patra, avouris@upatras.gr

On --, --, -- the members of the Homo Digitalis Project Management Committee (PMC) deliberated through **email correspondence** the final version of the Project Management Plan. It has been pondered that PMP is in line with the GA, WPs and requirements of the Project needed for operationalization.

The Project Management Plan has thus been approved with the consent of all members of the PMC. As the supplement to this document herein are added the screenshots of PMC's members' emails confirming that they agree with the latest Homo Digitalis Project Monitoring Plan.